

Policy Paper

*Recommendations for Equitable and
Sustainable AI Adoption in European Retail SMEs*

Increasing the uptake of AI in Retail
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Abstract	This policy paper synthesises findings and strategic recommendations derived from the INAIR project - a European Union-funded initiative dedicated to fostering AI integration within European retail small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). While the integration of artificial intelligence is instrumental for enhancing competitiveness and long-term sustainability, its widespread adoption faces multifaceted challenges. The document analyses the barriers to AI adoption, including the existing policy limitations and structural complexities that may inadvertently contribute to uneven technological adoption across the sector. To facilitate an equitable, trustworthy, and scalable diffusion of AI, this paper advocates for a coordinated multi-stakeholder strategy involving policymakers, the retail industry, and educational institutions. It delineates targeted recommendations centered on fostering inclusive training, promoting lifelong learning, strengthening ethical AI governance, and establishing sustainable funding and collaborative frameworks.
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KEY MESSAGES

- AI adoption in retail MSMEs depends on more than access to AI tools. It requires digital infrastructure, usable data, managerial capacity, workforce skills and organisational readiness
- Many smaller retailers still need to strengthen basic digital systems, including ERP, CRM, e-commerce, data collection and process integration, before advanced AI solutions can create real value.
- Training should be practical, modular, multilingual and role-specific. Retail workers, managers, owners and trainers require different learning pathways linked to concrete retail functions.
- Trustworthy AI should be integrated into everyday business practice. Retail MSMEs need accessible guidance on transparency, data protection, fairness, human oversight, accountability and compliance with the GDPR and the EU AI Act.
- Public support should follow the full implementation cycle: assess digital readiness, strengthen infrastructure, develop skills, provide advisory support, create testing opportunities and offer targeted funding for responsible AI adoption.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this document

This policy paper provides evidence-based recommendations to support the equitable, trustworthy and sustainable adoption of artificial intelligence in European retail micro, small and medium-sized enterprises. It is intended to translate the findings and practical outputs of the INAIR (“INcreasing the uptake of AI in Retail”) project into policy-relevant guidance for institutions and stakeholders working on digital transformation, SME competitiveness, skills development, vocational education and training, labour market adaptation, sustainability and AI governance.

The document responds to a policy challenge: while AI can help retailers improve productivity, customer engagement, inventory management, decision-making, resource efficiency and competitiveness, many retail MSMEs remain insufficiently prepared to adopt and govern AI effectively. Barriers include uneven digital readiness, limited financial and organisational capacity, fragmented data systems, shortages of relevant skills, uncertainty about legal and ethical requirements, and low confidence in the practical value of AI for smaller businesses.

The purpose of this paper is therefore to identify the conditions that enable responsible AI adoption in retail and to propose policy measures that can help smaller retailers benefit from AI without deepening existing inequalities. It focuses on the practical requirements of implementation, including access to role-specific training, lifelong learning opportunities, advisory support, trustworthy AI guidance, sustainable funding mechanisms, cooperation between training providers and industry, and support for organisational change.

The paper does not treat AI adoption as a purely technological issue. Instead, it frames AI uptake as a wider transformation process involving people, skills, business models, governance, infrastructure and trust. Its recommendations aim to help policymakers and institutional actors create an enabling environment in which retail MSMEs can adopt AI in ways that are economically viable, socially responsible, compliant with European values and regulation, and aligned with sustainability objectives.

1.2 Target audience

This document is addressed primarily to policymakers and public authorities involved in digital transformation, SME policy, vocational education and training, labour market development, innovation support, consumer protection, sustainability and AI governance. This includes European institutions, national ministries, regional authorities, managing authorities for EU funds, digital innovation agencies, employment and skills bodies, and organisations responsible for implementing SME support programmes.

The paper is also relevant for chambers of commerce, retail associations, social partners, vocational education and training providers, higher education institutions, lifelong learning organisations, digital innovation hubs and other intermediary bodies that support retail companies in adopting new technologies.

These organisations play a central role in translating policy objectives into accessible training, guidance and advisory services for businesses.

Retail companies, especially micro, small and medium-sized retailers, are an additional target audience. While the document is written primarily for policymakers, its recommendations are designed to reflect the operational realities of retail firms, including limited time, financial resources and internal technical capacity. The paper may therefore support business owners, managers and HR or training leads in understanding which forms of public support, training provision and governance guidance are most relevant for responsible AI adoption.

Finally, the document may be useful for researchers, civil society organisations and technology providers interested in the social, economic and ethical implications of AI in retail. By presenting policy recommendations grounded in INAIR project results, it aims to contribute to a shared understanding of how AI can be adopted in ways that strengthen competitiveness while protecting workers, consumers and smaller businesses.

1.3 About the project

The INAIR (“INcreasing the uptake of AI in Retail”) project is a European initiative designed to help micro, small and medium-sized retailers strengthen their artificial intelligence capabilities and accelerate digital transformation. Funded through the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme, the project addresses the gap between the rapid development of AI technologies in retail and the relatively low adoption rates among European retail businesses. INAIR aims to equip retailers with the knowledge and practical skills needed to use AI effectively, improve competitiveness and support more sustainable business practices in line with the EU’s Digital Decade goals.

The project identified AI skills needs and gaps within the retail sector and developed targeted training and support solutions, including:

- an **AI Core Curriculum**¹ covering AI fundamentals, retail applications, sustainability and trustworthy AI;
- an **AI Skills Assessment Tool**² for retailers;
- a **multilingual e-learning environment**³ offering learning pathways differentiated by learners’ roles and proficiency levels;
- a **Practical Guide for Facilitators**⁴ to support the integration of INAIR resources into vocational education and training;

¹ Acomi, N., Lanzetta, M., ACOMI, O., Chervinskyi, M., Włoch, R., Śledziowska, K., Abbruzzese, G., Fotiadis, T., Andreotti, C., & Manchi, G. (2025). AI Core Curriculum for MSMEs in Retail. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14358284>

² <https://www.ai4retail.eu/en/initial-ai-assessment-tool>

³ <https://app.ai4retail.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.ai4retail.eu/en/practical-guide-facilitators>

- a **map of relevant web-based AI tools for retail MSMEs**⁵, assessed against requirements derived from the European Commission High-Level Expert Group's Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI.

Through workshops, research activities and pilot programmes, INAIR seeks to train and upskill retail employees and business owners, enabling them to integrate trustworthy and sustainable AI technologies into everyday operations.

Beyond training, INAIR supports ethical and human-centred AI adoption by helping retailers and training providers understand not only how AI can be used, but also under which organisational, legal and ethical conditions it should be implemented. The project results therefore provide a practical evidence base for the policy recommendations developed in this paper.

⁵ <https://www.ai4retail.eu/en/map-trustworthy-ai-tools>

2. Policy Context and Problem Definition

Artificial intelligence is increasingly becoming part of everyday retail operations. In retail, AI can support customer service, personalised recommendations, demand forecasting, inventory management, pricing, logistics, marketing, fraud detection, workforce planning, data-driven decision-making and business intelligence. Used responsibly, it can improve efficiency, help retailers respond to changing consumer expectations and contribute to more sustainable resource use. However, AI adoption in the retail sector remains uneven and, for many smaller firms, still at an early stage.

Effective AI adoption depends on a broader enabling environment that includes digital infrastructure, reliable and well-governed data, organisational readiness, managerial capacity, workforce skills, trust, legal clarity and access to finance. The INAIR evidence base indicates that many retail MSMEs are still consolidating foundational elements of digital transformation, including the use of ERP and CRM systems, e-commerce tools, cloud services, data collection systems and process automation infrastructure. In this context, the potential value of AI depends substantially on the quality, integration and governance of the data and systems into which AI applications are introduced.

The European policy context is shaped by the Digital Decade objective of increasing the uptake of advanced digital technologies among European enterprises. INAIR was designed to contribute to this objective, including the target that more than 75% of EU companies use AI, cloud or big data by 2030. However, available evidence indicates that the retail sector remains below this level: latest Eurostat data⁶ reveals that only 18.62% of wholesale and retail enterprises had implemented AI technologies in 2025, highlighting the distance between policy ambition and sectoral reality.

This gap is particularly important because the European retail sector is highly fragmented and largely composed of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises. The sector also shows considerable variation in levels of digitalisation across countries and firm sizes. INAIR's research⁷ indicates that such fragmentation can affect competitiveness, operational efficiency and the pace of digital transformation. These findings suggest that policy responses should be sensitive to national context, business size, retail function and the starting level of digital maturity of firms.

INAIR's research also identifies several recurring constraints on AI adoption in retail MSMEs, including limited specialised knowledge, high implementation costs, legal and regulatory uncertainty, and insufficient digital skills. These constraints are particularly relevant for smaller enterprises and for firms operating in less digitally mature environments. The policy problem is therefore multidimensional. Retailers need not only technical AI-related skills, but also the capacity to identify relevant use cases, assess risks and benefits,

⁶ Eurostat (2025). Artificial intelligence by NACE Rev. 2 activity. Online data code: isoc_eb_ain2. DOI: https://doi.org/10.2908/ISOC_EB_AIN2. Data updated as of 27/02/2026.

⁷ Włoch, R., Ślosarski, B., Paliński, M., Śledziwska, K., Teodorowicz, K., & Łebkowska, W. (2025). AI skills needs and gaps for MSMEs in the retail sector in Cyprus, Germany, Italy, Poland, and Romania. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17661155>

manage organisational change, comply with applicable regulation, involve workers, communicate transparently with customers and evaluate whether AI tools deliver measurable business, social and sustainability outcomes.

A further policy consideration is the risk that uneven AI adoption could reinforce existing disparities within the retail sector. Larger retailers may be better positioned to invest in AI-enabled systems, data infrastructure and specialist expertise, while smaller retailers may depend on fragmented, proprietary or externally controlled digital ecosystems. Without appropriate support, AI adoption could contribute to widening productivity gaps, increasing dependence on dominant technology platforms and reducing the ability of smaller firms to compete on fair terms. This underlines the importance of interoperable systems, sound data governance, transparent procurement practices and compliance with relevant legal frameworks, including the General Data Protection Regulation and the EU AI Act.

For these reasons, AI adoption in retail should be understood both as a business transformation issue and as a public policy concern. Public authorities, education and training providers, sectoral organisations, social partners, technology providers and retail companies have a shared interest in ensuring that AI adoption is inclusive, trustworthy, sustainable and economically viable. Policy intervention is justified where individual firms, particularly MSMEs, lack the resources, capabilities or incentives to invest in the skills, infrastructure, governance mechanisms and organisational transformation required for responsible AI adoption at scale.

3. Key Insights from the INAIR Project

3.1 AI adoption in retail is a competence challenge

Successful AI adoption in retail depends not only on the availability of technological tools, but also on the capacity of people and organisations to understand, select, use and govern those tools effectively. Retailers require staff who can work with data, interpret AI-generated outputs, assess automated recommendations critically, recognise system limitations and connect AI applications to concrete business needs. Managers require the ability to assess investment options, understand implementation risks, engage employees, organise adoption processes and evaluate outcomes.

AI adoption should therefore be understood as a collective organisational competence. Relevant capabilities include understanding customer needs, personalising offers responsibly, interpreting business data, assessing the quality and reliability of information, and adapting professional roles to a changing technological environment. This perspective shifts the focus from technology procurement alone to human and organisational capability-building.

INAIR research indicates that explicit employer demand for AI skills in retail remains limited. Many retailers continue to prioritise foundational digital skills, including the use of office software, ERP systems, CRM systems, e-commerce platforms, digital marketing tools and customer interaction capabilities. This does not reduce the importance of AI skills. Rather, it suggests that many retail MSMEs are still at an early stage of digital transformation and require a staged pathway from basic digital literacy to applied AI skills and, ultimately, strategic AI integration.

3.2 Retailers need role-specific and function-specific learning pathways

AI adoption affects different retail functions in different ways. Marketing teams may use AI for customer segmentation, personalised communication, recommendation systems and campaign analysis. Operations and logistics staff may use AI for demand forecasting, supply chain optimisation and stock management. Store managers may use AI to support staffing decisions, customer service and local performance monitoring. Owners and senior managers require strategic competence to assess business cases, governance risks and organisational readiness.

The INAIR learning model addresses this diversity through differentiated learning pathways. The e-learning environment assigns content according to the learner's professional role and the results of the initial assessment, recognising that AI adoption does not occur uniformly across sales, marketing, logistics, human resources, customer service, operations and management functions. Public training schemes and sectoral upskilling programmes should therefore avoid relying exclusively on generic AI awareness training and should promote role-specific, modular and applied learning pathways.

3.3 Practical, modular and multilingual training can improve confidence and readiness

The INAIR pilot provides evidence on the perceived relevance and usability of practical, modular and role-based AI training. By 23 April 2026, 242 participants had registered for the pilot and 75 had provided valid end-user evaluation responses. The pilot involved a structured learning pathway consisting of an initial assessment, assignment to a personalised pathway, completion of modular content and a final assessment.

The pilot results indicate that structured, applied and role-based AI training can be positively received by retail workers and business owners. According to the pilot evaluation, 84% of respondents indicated that the educational resources reflected real-world retail scenarios, 87% considered the module structure clear and easy to follow, 88% reported improved understanding of AI in retail, 85% reported increased confidence in considering or adopting AI-based solutions, and 72% stated that they intended to integrate AI-related tools or approaches as a result of participation.

These results should be interpreted with appropriate caution. The pilot data are self-reported and reflect the perceptions of respondents rather than representative evidence for the entire retail sector. Nevertheless, the findings support the value of scaling modular, multilingual, role-specific and work-relevant AI learning resources, particularly where these resources are embedded into broader organisational learning strategies.

3.4 Trustworthy AI must be treated as a core competence

Ethical and trustworthy AI should be treated as an integral part of AI skills, not as an optional or separate topic. In retail, AI can affect consumer choice, pricing, profiling, access to services, employee monitoring, scheduling, recruitment, customer communication and data protection. These are areas where trust, transparency and accountability are essential.

The AI Core Curriculum includes dedicated learning blocks on ethics, regulation and trustworthy AI. These components address transparency, accountability, privacy, the General Data Protection Regulation, the EU AI Act, ethical AI practices and the ability to interpret and apply regulatory requirements in practical scenarios. The curriculum also includes learning experiences such as AI risk assessment and classification, GDPR compliance workshops and case studies on the impact of the GDPR and the EU AI Act on businesses.

Retail MSMEs cannot be expected to interpret complex AI governance requirements without practical guidance, templates, training and sector-specific examples. Policy support should therefore include not only funding for AI adoption, but also accessible compliance support, standardised guidance for common retail use cases and mechanisms for building trust among workers and consumers.

3.5 AI adoption should support sustainability, not only productivity

AI adoption in retail should support competitiveness while also contributing to more sustainable business practices. The AI Core Curriculum addresses the fundamentals of AI and its applications for greening retail businesses, optimising resources and improving processes. It also includes a dedicated learning block on AI for sustainability, covering both the use of AI to support sustainability objectives and the sustainability implications of AI itself in retail MSMEs.

This dual perspective is important for policy. AI can support waste reduction, improve inventory accuracy, optimise logistics and enable more efficient use of resources. At the same time, AI systems may increase energy consumption, require large volumes of data and raise concerns about the environmental costs of computing and data storage. Sustainable AI adoption in retail therefore requires attention to both the potential benefits and the resource implications of AI deployment.

Policy should encourage AI adoption that is aligned with environmental objectives and responsible innovation. Funding and guidance should prioritise AI use cases that demonstrate measurable value for resource efficiency, waste reduction, operational resilience and sustainable customer engagement, while discouraging unnecessary, poorly governed or low-value deployment.

4. Key Barriers to AI Implementation

4.1 Competence gaps at operational and strategic levels

One of the most significant barriers to AI implementation in retail MSMEs is the lack of digital and AI-related competence. This gap exists at both operational and strategic levels. Employees may lack the skills needed to work with data, interpret AI-generated outputs, assess information quality or use available tools in daily tasks. Managers may lack the knowledge needed to identify viable AI use cases, assess costs and benefits, understand limitations, manage risk, select trustworthy providers and lead organisational change.

Limited skills can create a reinforcing cycle. Where firms lack the capacity to understand and implement digital technologies, they may also be less likely to demand advanced skills or invest in AI-related training. This can contribute to persistently low levels of digitalisation and delayed AI adoption. Policy should therefore stimulate both the supply of and demand for applied AI skills.

The evidence suggests that many retailers require stronger foundational digital skills before advanced AI training can be effective. Demand in retail often remains focused on basic digital literacy, office software, ERP and CRM systems, e-commerce tools and digital marketing skills rather than explicit AI skills. Training policy should therefore follow a staged approach: basic digital readiness, data literacy, applied AI awareness, role-specific AI use, and strategic integration and governance.

4.2 Financial constraints and uncertain return on investment

Financial constraints are a major barrier to AI adoption, particularly for micro and small retailers. AI implementation may involve direct costs for software, cloud services, data integration, technical support and consultancy, as well as indirect costs related to training, staff time, process redesign, compliance and organisational change. For smaller firms operating with limited margins, these costs may appear high and the return on investment uncertain.

Limited financial resources and difficulties accessing external finance can lead firms to postpone AI implementation or restrict adoption to basic, low-cost tools. While such tools may provide some immediate benefits, they may not support deeper transformation of business processes or generate sustained long-term value.

Policy should therefore distinguish between experimental AI use and meaningful AI adoption. Funding should not be limited to isolated tool purchases. It should support integrated packages that combine infrastructure, training, advisory services, governance support, testing environments and follow-up evaluation. Innovation vouchers, blended finance, tax incentives and regional support schemes should reduce risk for smaller retailers while requiring clear learning, governance and sustainability objectives.

4.3 Infrastructure, data quality and system integration

AI systems require usable data and appropriate digital infrastructure. Many retail MSMEs still lack integrated systems for inventory, sales, customer relationship management, e-commerce, logistics, finance and workforce planning. Data may be incomplete, inconsistent, dispersed across systems or stored in formats that are not suitable for analysis. Under these conditions, AI tools are unlikely to deliver their full potential value.

ERP and CRM systems, cloud solutions, data collection and integration tools, and process automation infrastructure are important prerequisites for effective AI implementation. AI effectiveness depends on data quality, system integration and appropriate governance. Where data are scattered, incomplete or inconsistent, AI applications may remain limited to narrow or low-impact use cases.

AI support for retail MSMEs should therefore be linked to broader digital transformation support. Programmes that focus only on AI tools may be ineffective if firms lack the underlying digital foundations. Policymakers should promote integrated digital readiness assessments, common data standards, interoperable solutions and affordable access to trusted infrastructure.

4.4 Organisational capacity and change management

AI adoption requires changes in work organisation, decision-making and management practices. Retailers need to define use cases, redesign workflows, involve workers, monitor impacts, evaluate tool performance, communicate with customers and ensure compliance with legal and ethical requirements. Many smaller companies lack dedicated transformation teams or specialised technical staff to manage this process.

Limited organisational capacity can lead to fragmented or piecemeal implementation. Firms may adopt individual tools without a coherent strategy, without adequate monitoring of results and without sufficient integration into existing processes. This can reduce the likelihood that AI adoption will produce lasting organisational or economic benefits.

Practical and low-threshold support is therefore needed. Facilitators, trainers, chambers of commerce, digital innovation hubs, vocational education and training providers, and other intermediary organisations can play an important role in helping smaller retailers understand AI use cases, prepare staff, assess risks and integrate AI-related learning into daily business practice.

4.5 Trust, transparency and social acceptance

Retail AI systems may affect employees and customers in sensitive ways. Automated recommendations, personalised pricing, customer profiling, chatbots, employee monitoring, scheduling tools and AI-supported recruitment can raise concerns about privacy, fairness, transparency and accountability. If these concerns are not addressed, AI adoption may face resistance from workers, consumers or managers.

Trust issues may arise both inside companies and in customer relationships. Retailers need to understand when and how automated systems should be disclosed, how personal data should be protected, how AI-generated outputs should be reviewed, and how responsibility should be assigned when automated systems influence decisions. Risks may also relate to job displacement, inaccurate AI inferences or predictions, environmental impacts and the absence of clear industry standards.

Trust-building should therefore be embedded into AI adoption support from the outset. Retailers need practical guidance on transparency, human oversight, data protection, bias mitigation, explainability and employee involvement. Social dialogue should be encouraged where AI affects work organisation, task redesign, performance management or workplace monitoring.

5. Policy Gaps and Structural Problems

The adoption of artificial intelligence in European retail MSMEs is shaped by a set of structural conditions that extend beyond the capacity of individual firms. While many retailers can take steps to improve their own digital readiness, several barriers require coordinated action by public authorities, education and training providers, sectoral organisations, social partners, technology providers and business support institutions. These barriers concern the availability and accessibility of support schemes, the uneven distribution of digital infrastructure and skills, the complexity of regulatory compliance, and the risk of dependency on external digital ecosystems.

5.1 Fragmented support schemes and limited accessibility for smaller retailers

Public and private support for digitalisation, innovation and skills development is available in many European countries. However, these schemes are often fragmented across different institutions, funding instruments, policy areas and administrative levels. Retail MSMEs may face difficulties identifying the most relevant support opportunities, understanding eligibility criteria, completing administrative procedures or combining funding for training, advisory services, infrastructure and implementation.

This fragmentation is particularly challenging for micro and small retailers, which often lack dedicated staff for grant applications, innovation management or digital transformation planning. As a result, firms that already have stronger managerial and administrative capacity are more likely to benefit from existing programmes, while less digitally mature firms may remain excluded. This can contribute to unequal access to AI-related support and may reinforce existing differences between larger and smaller firms, as well as between regions with different levels of institutional capacity.

A more coherent policy approach is needed to make support easier to access, especially for firms at the beginning of their digital transformation journey. This includes clearer signposting, simplified administrative procedures, integrated advisory services and one-stop-shop models that combine digital readiness assessment, skills guidance, funding information and implementation support.

5.2 Unequal access to digital infrastructure, data capacity and trusted tools

AI adoption depends on the availability of appropriate digital infrastructure, data systems and reliable tools. Many retail MSMEs still require investment in basic digital foundations before AI can be used effectively. These foundations include connectivity, cloud services, ERP and CRM systems, e-commerce platforms, data collection tools, cybersecurity measures and interoperable business systems.

Unequal access to these foundations creates unequal opportunities for AI adoption. Firms with integrated data systems and stronger digital infrastructure can more easily identify use cases, test AI applications and

evaluate results. Firms with fragmented or low-quality data, limited connectivity or outdated systems may not be able to use AI tools effectively, even where such tools are technically available.

This raises a structural policy issue. AI support programmes that focus only on the purchase or use of AI tools may have limited impact if firms lack the underlying digital conditions required for implementation. Policy measures should therefore link AI adoption to broader digital transformation support, including data readiness, interoperability, cybersecurity, system integration and access to trusted digital infrastructure.

5.3 Gaps in structured AI skills pathways for managers and workers

Skills shortages remain one of the most significant barriers to responsible AI adoption in retail. However, the problem is not only the absence of advanced technical expertise. Many retail MSMEs require structured pathways that connect basic digital literacy, data literacy, applied AI awareness, role-specific AI use, organisational change management and trustworthy AI governance.

Existing training provision is often too general, too technical or insufficiently adapted to the daily realities of retail work. Generic AI awareness sessions may raise interest but do not necessarily equip workers and managers to apply AI in areas such as customer service, inventory management, marketing, logistics, pricing, business intelligence or workforce planning. At the same time, highly technical training may not be suitable for smaller retailers whose immediate needs relate to practical use cases, data interpretation, tool selection, risk assessment and implementation management.

Policy frameworks should therefore support modular, role-specific and work-based learning pathways. These should address the different needs of owners, managers, frontline workers, marketing staff, logistics staff, administrative teams and training providers. Skills policies should also recognise that AI skills are not a one-off training outcome, but a continuous learning requirement as technologies, regulations and business models evolve.

5.4 Insufficient visibility and recognition of AI-related competences

A further gap concerns the visibility and recognition of AI-related skills in retail. Employers may not always be able to define the AI skills they need, while workers may lack recognised ways to demonstrate newly acquired skills. This limits the ability of training providers to design targeted programmes and reduces the incentives for workers and employers to invest in upskilling.

In many retail contexts, AI-related competence is closely linked to broader digital, data and organisational skills. These include understanding data quality, interpreting automated outputs, using AI-enabled tools responsibly, communicating with customers about digital services, identifying operational use cases and recognising ethical or legal risks. If these competences are not clearly defined, assessed and recognised, they may remain invisible in recruitment, promotion, workforce development and training design.

Policy measures should support competence frameworks, micro-credentials and assessment tools that make AI-related skills more visible and portable. This would help align training provision with labour market needs and support more transparent skills development within the retail sector.

5.5 Regulatory complexity and limited practical compliance support

European regulatory frameworks, including the General Data Protection Regulation and the EU AI Act, are essential for ensuring that AI is used in ways that protect rights, safety and public trust. However, many retail MSMEs may find it difficult to translate legal requirements into practical organisational procedures, especially when using third-party AI tools embedded in customer service, marketing, pricing, HR, logistics or analytics systems.

The challenge is not only regulatory awareness. Smaller firms need practical guidance on how to classify AI use cases, manage data protection obligations, ensure transparency, maintain human oversight, assess risks, document decisions, evaluate vendors and communicate responsibly with workers and customers. Without accessible compliance support, smaller firms may either avoid AI adoption due to uncertainty or adopt tools without sufficient safeguards.

This creates a need for sector-specific guidance, templates and advisory services. Retail MSMEs require practical compliance resources that are proportionate to their size and risk profile, while still supporting high standards of transparency, accountability, non-discrimination, data protection and human oversight.

5.6 Limited trust and insufficient social dialogue

Trust is a central condition for AI adoption in retail. AI systems may influence customer interactions, personalised offers, pricing, profiling, employee scheduling, recruitment, performance monitoring and operational decision-making. These uses can create concerns among workers and consumers if they are not accompanied by transparency, safeguards and meaningful channels for feedback.

Low trust may slow adoption or generate resistance, particularly where employees perceive AI as a tool for surveillance, job replacement or intensified performance control. Consumers may also be concerned about how their data are collected, analysed and used in personalised services. These concerns are not incidental; they are part of the social conditions that determine whether AI can be implemented responsibly and sustainably.

Policy and sectoral initiatives should therefore encourage social dialogue and worker participation in AI adoption processes. Employees should be informed when AI systems affect their work, and companies should have procedures for explaining AI-enabled decisions, reviewing outputs and addressing concerns. Trust-building should be treated as part of implementation, not as a communication exercise after deployment.

5.7 Risk of dependency on dominant digital platforms and non-European ecosystems

Many smaller retailers rely on externally supplied digital platforms for e-commerce, marketing, payments, logistics, customer relationship management and analytics. AI functionalities are increasingly embedded in these platforms. While this can make AI tools more accessible, it may also increase dependency on proprietary systems, opaque algorithms, external data infrastructures and non-European technology providers.

This dependency can limit the ability of smaller retailers to control their data, understand system behaviour, switch providers or negotiate fair terms. It can also create risks for competition, interoperability and data sovereignty. Larger retailers may have the resources to develop or customise AI systems, while smaller firms may be locked into standardised platform-based solutions that offer limited transparency or flexibility.

Policy responses should promote interoperability, fair access to data, transparent contractual conditions and European digital solutions where appropriate. Support for open standards, trusted tool assessment, data spaces and shared sectoral infrastructures can help reduce the risk that AI adoption increases dependency rather than strengthening the autonomy and competitiveness of smaller retailers.

5.8 Insufficient alignment between AI adoption and sustainability objectives

AI is often promoted as a tool for improving productivity and efficiency, but its contribution to sustainability is not automatic. Retail AI applications can support more accurate demand forecasting, waste reduction, inventory optimisation, energy management, logistics planning and more efficient use of resources. However, AI systems also involve environmental costs related to data storage, computing power, model development and digital infrastructure.

Current support schemes do not always require firms to assess both the sustainability benefits and the environmental costs of AI deployment. As a result, AI adoption may focus on short-term efficiency or commercial objectives without sufficient attention to broader environmental and social outcomes.

Policy frameworks should encourage AI use cases that contribute to measurable sustainability objectives, including waste reduction, resource efficiency, circular economy practices and operational resilience. At the same time, guidance should help retailers avoid unnecessary or poorly justified AI deployment where simpler digital tools or process improvements may be more proportionate.

5.9 Need for coordinated governance and collective implementation capacity

The barriers identified above cannot be addressed effectively by individual retail firms acting alone. AI adoption in retail requires coordinated governance across policy domains, including digital transformation,

SME competitiveness, skills, labour market policy, consumer protection, sustainability, innovation and data governance.

Sectoral organisations, chambers of commerce, vocational education and training providers, higher education institutions, digital innovation hubs and social partners have an important role in translating policy objectives into practical support. They can help firms identify needs, access training, understand regulatory requirements, assess tools, exchange good practices and build trust.

A coordinated approach is needed to ensure that AI adoption in retail is not limited to technologically advanced firms or regions. Policy should support shared training infrastructures, trusted knowledge networks, practical advisory services, interoperable tools, recognised skills pathways and mechanisms for worker and consumer trust. Without such coordination, AI adoption is likely to remain uneven, fragmented and more difficult for smaller retailers to sustain.

6. Policy Recommendations

AI adoption in European retail MSMEs requires a coordinated policy approach that combines skills development, digital infrastructure, access to finance, trustworthy AI governance, organisational support and sustainability objectives. This chapter presents a set of recommendations addressed to policymakers, public authorities, education and training providers, sectoral organisations, social partners, intermediary bodies and retail companies. They are intended to support AI adoption that is practical, inclusive, trustworthy and aligned with the needs of smaller retailers.

Specifically, this paper delineates fifteen strategic recommendations, structured across four primary thematic policy packages:

Policy package 1: Skills and learning pathways

- Establish accessible AI upskilling pathways for retail MSMEs
- Support managers in leading responsible AI adoption
- Strengthen the role of vocational education and training providers
- Promote recognised AI competence frameworks and micro-credentials

Policy package 2: Implementation and funding support

- Link AI adoption support to broader digital readiness
- Provide targeted financial support for smaller retailers
- Support advisory and intermediary services for implementation
- Promote interoperability, data governance and fair access to digital infrastructure

Policy package 3: Trustworthy and sustainable AI governance

- Develop practical guidance on trustworthy AI for retail
- Encourage responsible procurement and assessment of AI tools
- Align AI adoption with sustainability objectives
- Foster worker involvement and social dialogue

Policy package 4: Coordination, monitoring and ecosystem building

- Build communities of practice and peer-learning networks
- Monitor outcomes and evaluate policy effectiveness
- Ensure coordination across policy areas and governance levels

POLICY PACKAGE 1: SKILLS AND LEARNING PATHWAYS

6.1 Establish accessible AI upskilling pathways for retail MSMEs

Public authorities and training institutions should support structured AI upskilling pathways tailored to the specific needs of retail MSMEs. Training should not be limited to general awareness of AI. It should enable owners, managers and employees to understand how AI can be applied in concrete retail functions, including customer service, marketing, inventory management, logistics, pricing, business intelligence, sustainability and workforce planning.

Training provision should follow a staged approach. Many retail MSMEs first require support with basic digital readiness, data literacy and the use of existing digital tools before they can benefit from more advanced AI-related training. AI upskilling should therefore progress from foundational digital skills to applied AI awareness, role-specific use cases, organisational implementation and governance.

Training programmes should also be modular and flexible. Retail MSMEs often face time constraints, limited staffing capacity and operational pressures. Short modules, self-paced learning, blended formats, practical exercises and work-based learning can make participation more feasible. Learning pathways should be differentiated by role and proficiency level, recognising that the needs of owners, managers, frontline workers, marketing staff, logistics staff, HR professionals and customer service employees are not identical.

Policy measures should support the integration of AI-related training into vocational education and training, continuing professional development, chamber of commerce programmes, sectoral initiatives and in-company learning. Public funding should prioritise programmes that are accessible to micro and small enterprises, available in national languages and linked to practical business applications.

6.2 Support managers in leading responsible AI adoption

Managers and owner-managers play a decisive role in AI adoption, particularly in smaller retail firms where strategic, operational and human resource decisions are often concentrated in a small number of people. Policy support should therefore include targeted training and advisory services for business leaders.

Managers need the capacity to identify relevant AI use cases, assess costs and benefits, understand data and infrastructure requirements, select trustworthy providers, evaluate risks, involve workers and monitor implementation outcomes. They also need to understand the legal, ethical and organisational implications of AI adoption, including data protection, transparency, human oversight and potential impacts on work organisation.

Public support programmes should include management-oriented AI readiness assessments, practical implementation guides, mentoring schemes and peer-learning formats. These measures can help managers move from general interest in AI to informed decision-making and responsible implementation. Particular

attention should be given to micro and small retailers that lack internal digital transformation teams or specialised technical staff.

6.3 Strengthen the role of vocational education and training providers

Vocational education and training providers are essential to scaling AI skills in the retail sector. Public authorities should support VET providers in updating curricula, developing applied AI modules, training educators and building partnerships with retail businesses.

AI-related training in VET should be practical, interdisciplinary and linked to real retail contexts. It should combine digital and data skills with business understanding, ethical reasoning, communication, problem-solving and sustainability. Training should help learners understand both the opportunities and limitations of AI, including how to interpret outputs, question automated recommendations and identify risks.

VET providers should be encouraged to work with retail associations, chambers of commerce, technology providers, social partners and higher education institutions. These partnerships can help ensure that training remains relevant to labour market needs and accessible to workers and firms with different levels of digital maturity.

Public funding should support the development of multilingual open educational resources, facilitator guides, assessment tools and micro-credentials. These resources can help make AI training scalable, reusable and adaptable across different national and regional contexts.

6.4 Promote recognised AI competence frameworks and micro-credentials

AI-related competences in retail should be made more visible, assessable and portable. Policymakers and education providers should support the development of competence frameworks and micro-credentials that reflect the practical skills needed by retail MSMEs.

These frameworks should cover both technical and transversal competences. Relevant areas include digital literacy, data literacy, understanding AI applications in retail, interpreting AI-generated outputs, assessing risks, using AI tools responsibly, understanding legal and ethical requirements, communicating transparently with customers and adapting work processes.

Micro-credentials can provide workers and employers with clearer evidence of skills acquisition. They can also help training providers design modular learning pathways and support employers in identifying relevant competences for recruitment, promotion and workforce development.

Recognition mechanisms should be designed to include workers at different starting levels. AI skills should not be limited to highly technical roles. Frontline employees, store managers, marketing staff, logistics staff, HR professionals and owner-managers all require different forms of AI-related competence.

POLICY PACKAGE 2: IMPLEMENTATION AND FUNDING SUPPORT

6.4 Link AI adoption support to broader digital readiness

AI policy measures for retail MSMEs should be integrated with broader digital transformation support. AI tools are unlikely to deliver meaningful value where firms lack reliable data, appropriate digital infrastructure, cybersecurity measures or integrated business systems.

Public programmes should therefore support digital readiness assessments before AI implementation. These assessments should examine the firm's existing use of digital systems, data quality, interoperability, cybersecurity, staff competences, organisational processes and governance capacity. Based on the results, firms should receive tailored guidance on the steps required before adopting AI-enabled tools.

Support should include access to affordable and interoperable digital infrastructure, including ERP and CRM systems, e-commerce platforms, cloud services, data collection tools and process automation systems. Policymakers should avoid treating AI adoption as a stand-alone objective. For many retail MSMEs, investment in foundational digital systems may be a necessary first step towards responsible and effective AI use.

6.5 Provide targeted financial support for smaller retailers

Financial constraints remain a major barrier to AI adoption among retail MSMEs. Public funding should reduce the risks and costs associated with responsible AI implementation, particularly for micro and small enterprises.

Financial instruments should support more than software acquisition. Effective AI adoption often requires a combination of training, advisory services, data preparation, system integration, cybersecurity, legal guidance, change management and evaluation. Funding schemes should therefore be designed as integrated support packages rather than isolated subsidies for technology purchases.

Possible instruments include innovation vouchers, tax incentives, grants, blended finance, regional digitalisation funds and subsidised advisory services. These instruments should be simple to access and proportionate to the administrative capacity of smaller firms. Application procedures should be streamlined, eligibility criteria should be clear, and support should be available through trusted intermediary organisations such as chambers of commerce, digital innovation hubs and sectoral associations.

Funding should prioritise AI use cases with clear potential to improve productivity, resource efficiency, customer service, resilience or sustainability. Public support should also require basic safeguards related to data protection, transparency, human oversight and compliance with applicable regulation.

6.6 Support advisory and intermediary services for implementation

Many retail MSMEs require hands-on support to move from training to implementation. Public policy should therefore strengthen the role of intermediary organisations that can provide practical, low-threshold assistance.

Chambers of commerce, retail associations, digital innovation hubs, VET providers, regional development agencies and social partners can help firms assess readiness, identify use cases, access funding, select tools, train staff, understand compliance obligations and evaluate outcomes. These organisations are particularly important for micro and small enterprises that lack internal technical capacity.

Advisory services should be neutral, accessible and tailored to the needs of smaller retailers. They should help firms avoid inappropriate or poorly governed AI adoption, including the purchase of tools that are not aligned with business needs, data capacity or regulatory obligations.

Public authorities should consider establishing one-stop-shop models for AI adoption in retail. These could combine readiness assessment, training guidance, funding advice, vendor-neutral tool information, compliance support and links to peer-learning opportunities.

6.7 Promote interoperability, data governance and fair access to digital ecosystems

AI adoption in retail depends on access to usable and well-governed data. Policymakers should promote interoperability, fair access to data and transparent conditions for the use of digital platforms and AI-enabled services.

Retail MSMEs should be supported in improving data quality, integrating business systems and applying sound data governance practices. Guidance should cover data collection, storage, access rights, consent, data minimisation, cybersecurity and responsible data sharing.

Policy should also address the risk that smaller retailers become overly dependent on dominant platforms or proprietary systems. Support for open standards, interoperable solutions and transparent contractual practices can help preserve the autonomy and competitiveness of smaller firms. Where appropriate, European data spaces and shared sectoral infrastructures should be explored as mechanisms to support trusted and secure data use in retail.

POLICY PACKAGE 3: TRUSTWORTHY AND SUSTAINABLE AI GOVERNANCE

6.8 Develop practical guidance on trustworthy AI for retail

Trustworthy AI should be embedded into all AI adoption support for retail MSMEs. Smaller retailers need practical and sector-specific guidance to understand how legal and ethical requirements apply to common retail use cases.

Public authorities and sectoral organisations should develop accessible guidance on issues such as data protection, transparency, profiling, personalised recommendations, automated customer service, pricing, employee monitoring, scheduling, recruitment, vendor selection and human oversight. Guidance should be written in clear language and include checklists, templates, examples and decision trees adapted to the realities of smaller firms.

Compliance support should cover relevant European frameworks, including the General Data Protection Regulation and the EU AI Act. Retailers should be supported in identifying whether an AI use case involves personal data, whether it may affect consumers or workers in sensitive ways, what level of human oversight is appropriate, and what documentation or risk assessment may be required.

Trustworthy AI guidance should not be presented only as a legal obligation. It should be framed as a condition for sustainable adoption, consumer confidence, worker acceptance and long-term business value.

6.9 Encourage responsible procurement and assessment of AI tools

Retail MSMEs often rely on externally supplied AI tools embedded in e-commerce platforms, customer relationship management systems, analytics tools, marketing software, logistics systems or workforce management applications. Policy support should help smaller firms assess these tools before adoption.

Responsible procurement guidance should include criteria for transparency, data protection, interoperability, cybersecurity, accessibility, vendor accountability, human oversight, explainability and sustainability. Retailers should be encouraged to ask whether tools are appropriate for their business needs, whether they require personal data, how outputs are generated, how risks are managed and whether the provider offers adequate documentation and support.

Public authorities and sectoral organisations could support the development of trusted catalogues, assessment templates or voluntary quality labels for AI tools used in retail MSMEs. Such resources should remain neutral and should not create barriers for smaller technology providers. The aim should be to improve informed decision-making and reduce the risk of dependency on opaque or unsuitable systems.

6.11 Align AI adoption with sustainability objectives

AI support for retail MSMEs should be aligned with environmental and social sustainability objectives. Public funding and advisory schemes should encourage AI use cases that contribute to measurable improvements in resource efficiency, waste reduction, inventory accuracy, logistics optimisation, energy management and operational resilience.

At the same time, policy should recognise that AI systems can involve environmental costs, including energy consumption, data storage and computing requirements. Retailers should be encouraged to assess whether AI is proportionate to the problem being addressed and whether simpler digital or organisational solutions may be more appropriate in some cases.

Sustainability criteria should be integrated into funding calls, training materials, procurement guidance and evaluation frameworks. AI adoption should be promoted where it creates clear value for both business performance and sustainable resource use.

6.12 Foster worker involvement and social dialogue

Responsible AI adoption requires the involvement of workers, particularly where AI affects work organisation, task allocation, monitoring, scheduling, recruitment, performance management or customer interaction. Policy frameworks should encourage social dialogue and participatory implementation processes.

Retailers should inform employees when AI systems are introduced, explain how these systems are used and provide opportunities for feedback. Workers should receive training not only on how to use AI tools, but also on how to question outputs, report problems and understand their rights and responsibilities.

Social partners can play an important role in developing sectoral guidance, supporting worker participation and ensuring that AI adoption contributes to better work organisation rather than increasing insecurity, surveillance or work intensity. Trustworthy AI adoption should therefore include both technical safeguards and workplace dialogue.

POLICY PACKAGE 4: COORDINATION, MONITORING AND ECOSYSTEM BUILDING

6.13 Build communities of practice and peer-learning networks

Retail MSMEs can benefit from opportunities to learn from other firms that have tested or implemented AI solutions. Policymakers and sectoral organisations should support communities of practice where retailers, trainers, technology providers and public institutions can exchange experiences, practical lessons and implementation challenges.

Peer-learning networks can help smaller retailers understand realistic AI use cases, avoid common mistakes, identify trusted support services and evaluate the practical value of different tools. They can also help disseminate good practices across regions and countries.

Communities of practice should include firms at different levels of digital maturity. This can support mutual learning and prevent AI policy from focusing only on highly advanced businesses. Particular attention should be given to micro and small retailers, rural and local businesses, and firms operating in less digitally mature regions.

6.14 Monitor outcomes and evaluate policy effectiveness

AI adoption support should include mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation. Policymakers should assess not only the number of firms receiving support, but also the quality and outcomes of adoption.

Relevant indicators may include improvements in digital readiness, participation in AI training, skills acquisition, implementation of trustworthy AI practices, worker involvement, business performance, sustainability outcomes, data governance maturity and continued use of AI tools after initial funding ends.

Evaluation should also examine distributional effects. Policy measures should assess whether support reaches micro and small retailers, less digitally mature firms, workers with lower levels of digital skills and regions with weaker innovation ecosystems. Without such monitoring, AI support may primarily benefit firms that are already better prepared.

Evidence from monitoring and evaluation should be used to adjust programmes over time. AI technologies, market conditions and regulatory requirements are evolving rapidly, and policy measures should remain adaptive.

6.15 Ensure coordination across policy areas and governance levels

AI adoption in retail intersects with several policy domains, including digital transformation, SME competitiveness, skills, employment, innovation, consumer protection, sustainability, data governance and

regulation. Effective support therefore requires coordination across ministries, agencies, regional authorities, education systems and sectoral bodies.

European, national and regional initiatives should be aligned to avoid duplication, fragmentation and administrative complexity. Coordination should support clear pathways for firms, from awareness and readiness assessment to training, funding, implementation, compliance and evaluation.

A coordinated policy approach should also ensure that AI adoption in retail remains inclusive. The objective should not be limited to increasing the number of firms using AI. Policy should support adoption that strengthens competitiveness, protects workers and consumers, reduces inequalities between firms and regions, and contributes to sustainable economic development.

7. Conclusions

Artificial intelligence has the potential to support the competitiveness, resilience and sustainability of European retail MSMEs. In retail, AI-enabled tools can contribute to better customer service, more accurate demand forecasting, improved inventory management, more efficient logistics, enhanced business intelligence and more sustainable use of resources. However, these benefits are not automatic. They depend on the capacity of firms to adopt AI in ways that are purposeful, proportionate, trustworthy and aligned with their organisational needs.

The evidence from the INAIR project shows that AI adoption in retail should not be understood primarily as a technology procurement issue. It is a broader transformation process involving skills, infrastructure, data governance, managerial capacity, worker involvement, trust, finance and regulatory compliance. Many retail MSMEs are still building the foundational digital capabilities needed to benefit from AI, including integrated data systems, e-commerce tools, cloud services, CRM and ERP systems, and basic digital and data literacy. For these firms, AI adoption requires a staged and supported pathway rather than one-off access to tools.

A central conclusion is that AI skills must be developed across the organisation. Owners and managers need the ability to identify relevant use cases, assess risks and benefits, select trustworthy providers, comply with regulation and lead organisational change. Employees need practical skills to use AI-enabled tools, interpret outputs, recognise limitations and apply human judgement. Training should therefore be role-specific, modular, multilingual and closely linked to real retail functions. Generic AI awareness activities are useful only as a starting point; they should be complemented by applied learning pathways and practical implementation support.

Trustworthy AI governance is also essential. Retail AI systems may affect customers, workers and business decisions in sensitive areas such as profiling, personalised recommendations, pricing, recruitment, scheduling, customer communication and employee monitoring. For this reason, transparency, accountability, data protection, human oversight and worker involvement should be embedded into AI adoption from the outset. Compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation and the EU AI Act should be supported through practical, sector-specific guidance that smaller firms can understand and apply.

The paper also underlines the risk that uneven AI adoption could deepen existing disparities in the retail sector. Larger companies are generally better placed to invest in data infrastructure, specialist expertise and advanced digital systems, while smaller retailers may face financial, organisational and skills-related constraints. Without targeted support, AI adoption may widen productivity gaps, increase dependency on dominant technology platforms and reduce the ability of smaller firms to compete. Public policy should therefore focus not only on increasing AI uptake, but also on ensuring that adoption is inclusive and accessible to firms with different levels of digital maturity.

Sustainability should be treated as a core policy objective of AI adoption in retail. AI can support resource efficiency, waste reduction, inventory optimisation and more resilient operations. At the same time, AI deployment can involve environmental costs linked to data processing, storage and computing

infrastructure. Policy measures should therefore encourage proportionate and purposeful AI use, prioritising applications that demonstrate measurable value for both business performance and environmental objectives.

The INAIR project provides a practical evidence base for this policy agenda. Its research on AI skills needs and gaps, AI Core Curriculum, AI Skills Assessment Tool, e-learning environment, Practical Guide for Facilitators, pilot activities and assessment of web-based AI tools demonstrate how research, training and implementation support can be connected. These outputs can inform future public programmes, sectoral initiatives and education and training provision aimed at supporting responsible AI adoption in retail MSMEs.

The overall policy message is clear: responsible AI adoption in retail requires coordinated action. Public authorities, education and training providers, chambers of commerce, retail associations, social partners, technology providers and companies should work together to create an enabling environment for smaller retailers. This includes accessible skills pathways, targeted financial support, trusted advisory services, interoperable infrastructure, practical compliance guidance, recognised competences, worker involvement and continuous monitoring of outcomes.

AI adoption should not be pursued as an end in itself. Its value lies in whether it helps retail MSMEs become more competitive, resilient, sustainable and capable of serving customers and workers in fair and trustworthy ways. A policy framework that combines innovation with inclusion, trust and sustainability will be essential to ensuring that the benefits of AI are accessible across Europe's diverse retail ecosystem.

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